

ON DIGITAL ESTIMATION OF THE INSTANTANEOUS FREQUENCY BEYOND THE FOLDING FREQUENCY

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to demonstrate the ability of the proposed time domain and frequency domain instantaneous frequency (IF) estimators to track with high accuracy the very dynamically varying IF of a discrete-time signal. Our experiments with the analysis of small birds songs show that both these estimators enable to follow the IF which extends beyond the signal spectral range as well as beyond the spectral folding frequency.

1. INTRODUCTION

Instantaneous frequency (IF) of a signal is one of the most important concepts in the field of time-frequency signal analysis and processing. It can provide new or additional information about the inner structure or local content of the signal in time in a variety of applications from communications, metrology and FM telemetry to the analysis of real-life signals [1] - [8]. Because of that the IF estimation has become the subject of interest of many authors (see, e.g., the references provided in [1], [6] and [8]).

2. BASIC DEFINITIONS

The IF of a signal is usually defined in the continuous-time domain. In practice, however, the IF estimation is performed either in the discrete-time domain using digital filters [2] or in the discrete-frequency domain via FFT [8].

In the continuous-time domain we normally deal with real-valued signals. Let $x(t)$, $-\infty < t < \infty$ be such a signal whose IF has to be estimated. First of all we have to create a complex analytic signal (AS) $u(t)$ corresponding to $x(t)$. It is a signal such that its imaginary component $y(t)$ is the Hilbert transform of the real component $x(t)$, as given by

$$u(t) \stackrel{\Delta}{=} x(t) + jy(t) \quad (1)$$

where

$$y(t) = H_H \{x(t)\} \quad (2)$$

The linear operator $H_H \{\}$ in (2) stands for the Hilbert transformer whose frequency response is

$$H_H(j2\pi f) \stackrel{\Delta}{=} -j \operatorname{sgn}(f), \quad -\infty < f < \infty \quad (3)$$

Now we can define the instantaneous frequency of the AS $u(t)$ (1). This can be done in the following way [8]

$$f_i(t) \stackrel{\Delta}{=} \frac{1}{2\pi} \operatorname{Im} \frac{du(t)}{u(t)} \quad (4)$$

Otherwise the IF $f_i(t)$ can be expressed in terms of its real valued Cartesian components: $x(t)$ and $y(t)$, and their derivatives over the continuous-time variable t , as given by

$$f_i(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{x(t) \frac{dy(t)}{dt} - y(t) \frac{dx(t)}{dt}}{x^2(t) + y^2(t)} \quad (5)$$

Both formulas: (4) and (5) are good candidates for digitisation.

3. THE PROPOSED IF ESTIMATORS

Based on (4) and (5) we have implemented in MATLAB two discrete IF estimators for the processing of the complex discrete-time AS

$$u[n] \stackrel{\Delta}{=} u(t) \Big|_{t=nT} = x[n] + jy[n] \quad (6)$$

It is a version of $u(t)$ discretised with the sampling period T .

In our discrete-time domain IF estimator based on the following approximation of (5) [9]

$$f_{iN}[n] = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{H_N \{x[n]\} D_N \{y[n]\} - H_N \{y[n]\} D_N \{x[n]\}}{(H_N \{x[n]\})^2 + (H_N \{y[n]\})^2} \quad (7)$$

we have used a digital FIR differentiating filter D_N of length N [4] such that

$$D_N \{u[n]\} \cong \frac{du(t)}{dt} \Big|_{t=(n-(N-1)/2)T} \quad (8)$$

The operator H_N has to align the differentiated waveform with its original counterpart involved in (7) in the following way

$$H_N \{u[n]\} \cong u(t) \Big|_{t=(n-(N-1)/2)T} \quad (9)$$

This FIR operator in the case of N odd stands simply for an integer delay of $(N-1)/2$ sample intervals.

The second IF estimator aimed at the block-by-block processing was implemented in the discrete-frequency

domain based on the following complex approximation of (4)

$$f_{iMK}[n] = \frac{1}{2\pi} \text{Im} \frac{u_{iMK}[n]}{u_M[n]} \quad (10)$$

where

$$u_{iMK}[n] = TR_M \{ IDFT_K \{ D_K[k] \cdot DFT_K \{ ZP_K \{ u_M[n] \} \} \} \}$$

and $u_M[n]$ is a block of M complex signal $u(n)$ samples. In this estimator we have used the discrete-frequency domain version of the differentiator

$$D_K[k] = \begin{cases} j2\pi k / K, & k = -(K/2-1), \dots, 0, \dots, K/2-1 \\ 0, & k = -K/2 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where K stands for the DFT length; $K \geq M$ and M is the length of a single block, as above. The symbols: DFT_K , $IDFT_K$, ZP_K and TR_M stand for the K -point discrete Fourier transformation, inverse discrete Fourier transformation, the operation of zero-padding the input sequence $u[n]$ from the length M to K and the inverse operation of truncating the output sequence from K to M , respectively.

4. EXPERIMENTS

In our experiments we have used the IF estimators from Sect.3 for the IF estimation of small birds' songs. These birds were: a barn owl and a canary. The recordings comprising one pseudoperiod for the song of each bird discretised with the sampling frequency 22,050 kHz are presented in Figs.1a and 2a.

Fig.1b presents the power spectrum of the song. Fig.1c convincingly demonstrates that the IF of the signal exceeds the Nyquist band ranging here from $-11,025$ kHz to $11,025$ kHz. The mean value of the IF from Fig.1c, shown in Fig.1d by thick line, was obtained by passing the IF waveform through an averaging FIR filter. This filter was designed based on the normalised von Hann window of length $M=64$. The filter has the total sum of the impulse response samples' values normalised to unity. Fig.1e shows the IF estimation error obtained by using the discrete-time domain method with the maximally flat differentiating FIR filter of length 21. The error is given in percent relative to that from the other method based on the FFT of length $K=8096$. The time-frequency relations are depicted in Fig.1f. The spectrogram there was obtained by using the von Hann window of length 64 (2.9 s of time) and with the 50% overlapping factor. The black line seen on the spectrogram represents the centroid of the instantaneous power spectrum waveform. The centroid facilitates estimation of monochromaticity of the mean IF obtained from the averaging filter.

Fig. 2 shows the respective waveforms and spectra for the canary song in the arrangement the same as in Fig.1.

Generally, the mean IF waveform is very close to the centroid for both signals being analysed. It is well illustrated by the narrowband song of canary. The barn owl song is a two-modal signal. Consequently its IF waveform reveals a number of „jumps” whose values exceed the

maximal value of the signal spectral frequency. As a result the mean IF waveform has some oscillations around the centroid.

Fig.1. Continued on the next page.

d)

a)

e)

b)

f)

c)

Fig.1. The recording (a) of one pseudoperiod of a barn owl song, the periodogram (b) computed for the above recording, the IF (c) and a strip of the IF (d) together with the mean IF (solid line), the relative error in % (e) between the two estimates and the spectrogram (f).

Fig.2. Continued on the next page.

Fig.2. A canary song and its analysis.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the paper two instantaneous frequency estimators: one of them acting in the discrete-time domain and the other in the discrete-frequency domain, were presented. It was shown on the examples of the processing of real-life signals that these estimators are effective in tracking the IF which extends beyond the signal spectral range as well as beyond the spectral folding frequency. The accuracy of the IF estimation depends on the length of digital FIR differentiating filters used in the discrete-time domain estimator and on the FFT length in the case of the discrete-frequency domain estimator.

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